

PERFORMANCE IMPROVEMENT OF TYPE-4 HYDROGEN PRESSURE VESSEL USING PROGRESSIVE PLY FAILURE MECHANISM

Akash Kumar Buroolia¹, Rajeev Kumar Verma¹ and Swati Neogi¹

¹Department of Chemical Engineering, Indian Institute of Technology Kharagpur
P.O. Paschim Medinipur, West Bengal-721302, India

Email: akashburoolia@gmail.com , web page: <https://www.iitkgp.ac.in/department/CH/faculty/ch-swati>

Email: rajeev0iitkgp@gmail.com , web page: <https://www.iitkgp.ac.in/department/CH/faculty/ch-swati>

Email: swati@che.iitkgp.ac.in , web page: <https://www.iitkgp.ac.in/department/CH/faculty/ch-swati>

Keywords: Hydrogen storage, Type-4 pressure vessel, genetic algorithm, classical laminate theory (CLT), Failure theories

ABSTRACT

This study presents an analytical and optimization-based approach to enhance the burst performance of type-4 hydrogen pressure vessels. An analytical model using Classical Laminate Theory (CLT) was developed and validated against experimental and finite element data (FEA) from Sharma et al. (2023), showing strong agreement with less than 1% error compared to FEA and 8.3% deviation from experimental burst pressure. Among various failure theories, Hashin criterion accurately predicted matrix dominated failure in the cylindrical section, consistent with experimental observations. To improve structural performance, a Progressive Ply Failure (PPF) strategy was first applied by replacing the first failed plies, resulting in a 16.28% increase in burst pressure. However, to achieve optimal stacking efficiency, a Genetic Algorithm (GA) was employed. Through iterative evolution using tournament selection, the GA achieved a 28.89% improvement in burst pressure compared to the reference model using Hashin failure. This combined approach of analytical modeling, failure prediction, and evolutionary optimization provides a reliable and scalable method for designing high-performance hydrogen storage vessels, supporting the advancement of safe and efficient clean energy systems.

1. INTRODUCTION

Compressed hydrogen is an emerging energy carrier for sustainable and clean energy systems, specifically for fuel cell vehicles (FCVs). The major challenge in hydrogen adoption is the safe and efficient hydrogen storage for onboard and stationary automobile applications. Moreover, hydrogen gas have high diffusivity ($6.1 \times 10^{-5} \text{ m}^2/\text{s}$ at NTP), reactivity, wide flammability range (4 - 74 % v/v in air) and low volumetric storage density (0.089 kg/m^3) at atmospheric condition which resist the commercialization of FCVs [1]. Therefore, hydrogen gas needs to be compressed and stored in pressure vessels at higher pressure up to 100 MPa, to improve the volumetric storage density.

There are four types of pressure vessels categories based on their material of construction as shown in Figure 1 (A). Type-1 is a traditional metallic pressure vessel with an operating pressure of ≤ 20 MPa. These vessels are highly prone to hydrogen embrittlement and their strength-to-weight ratio is very low. Type-2 pressure vessels are upgraded with hoop winding over a metallic liner/vessel, these vessels can hold the operating pressure up to ≤ 30 MPa. Type-3 is hybrid pressure vessels with fully overwrapped with hoop and helical layers over a metallic liner, these vessels have operating pressure up to ≤ 50 MPa. Type-4 is lightest among all the pressure vessels due to their material of construction, these vessels are fully overwrapped on a high hydrogen gas barrier polymeric liner. Type-4 pressure vessels have higher operating pressure up to 100 MPa, offers higher volumetric storage density and protected from hydrogen embrittlement. However, the major challenge in type-4 composite pressure vessels is the design of the composite structure because composite is the main strength contributor whereas the liner is a non-load

sharing component which is used to hold the hydrogen gas under allowable permeation rate and providing mandrel for filament winding [2], [3]. Composite structure of the pressure is composed of many hoop (90° angle layer) and helical layers (other than 90° angle layer) arranged in a specific order to achieve the desirable burst performance of the pressure vessels as shown in Figure 1 (B). These layers can be arranged in several ways to achieve the desired burst performance. The structural integrity and burst performance of Type-IV vessels are highly dependent on the stacking sequence of the composite layers. An optimized laminate design not only improves safety and reliability but also enhances material efficiency and reduces cost.

Figure 1: (A) Types of pressure vessel and (B) cross-sectional view of composite in type-4.

Several studies have been reported on the performance improvement of composites. Leh et al. developed a simulation platform to predict the burst pressure of type-4 pressure vessels using progressive failure mechanism. However, model was based conventional approach [4]. Nebe et al. investigate the burst pressure of composite pressure vessel based on first ply failure mechanism and found 67 % difference in experimental and model prediction [5]. Chang et al. worked on experimental validation of progressive ply failure using acoustic emission AMS3 (AE) system. However, his work does not involve any specific optimization technique [6]. The literature found that the progressive failure is a powerful approach for preliminary investigation of burst pressure and design. However, for fast and reliable designing of pressure vessel required a robust optimization technique to optimize the vessel design specifically layer sequence.

Alcantar et al. worked on optimization of type-4 pressure vessels using genetic algorithms and simulated annealing. the study reported 11.2 % improvement in design performance [7]. Fanding et al. integrated an artificial neural network with a finite element model to predict the first performance, and the model was accurate up to 2% of error [8].

Based on extensive literature, designing of composite pressure vessel with an optimum winding sequence for better performance is the major challenge. To address this challenge, this study integrates an analytical model based on Classical Laminate Theory (CLT) with failure criteria and optimization algorithms to improve vessel performance. The model is validated against experimental and finite element burst pressure data. A Progressive ply failure (PPF) approach is initially applied to iteratively enhance the layer sequence. However, due to its limitations, a Genetic Algorithm (GA) is introduced to perform a global optimization of the stacking sequence under mechanical and manufacturing constraints. This research aims to demonstrate the effectiveness of combining analytical modeling, failure analysis, and evolutionary optimization in designing high-performance Type-IV pressure vessels that meet stringent safety standards, such as ISO 11119-3. The findings provide a framework for systematic laminate optimization and support the advancement of safer, lighter, and more efficient hydrogen storage systems.

2. MATERIALS AND METHOD

2.1. MATERIALS

T700SC-12k carbon fiber manufactured by Toray, Japan and Araldite LY556 with hardener XY54 manufactured by Huntsman were used for the manufacturing of the type-4 pressure vessels. The composite properties were calculated by using micromechanics, measured properties are listed in Table 1 [9]. The fiber volume fraction of the composite material was 30 v/v%, measured by using muffle furnace by heating the small coupon of the composite at 600 °C temperature.

Table 1: Carbon-epoxy composite material specifications.

Properties	Symbol/unit	Carbon fiber (T700SC)	Epoxy resin Araldite LY 556 Hardener XY 54	Composite
Longitudinal modulus	E_{11} (MPa)	230000	3450	71415
Transverse modulus	E_{22} (MPa)	17000	3450	6123
In-plane shear modulus	G_{12} (MPa)	900	1280	2414
Out of plane shear modulus	G_{23} (MPa)	4600	1280	1383
Major Poisson's ratio	ν_{12}	0.2	0.35	0.305
Minor Poisson's ratio	ν_{23}	0.25	0.35	0.555
Longitudinal Tensile strength	X_{11}^t (MPa)	4900	90	1470
Transverse tensile strength	X_{22}^t (MPa)	-	90	88.5
In-plane shear strength	X_{12} (MPa)	600	50	118
Out of plane shear strength	X_{23} (MPa)	600	50	98
Density	ρ (kg/m ³)	1800	1150	1345

2.2. METHODS

In this study, the type-4 pressure vessel design parameters were taken from Sharma et al. [9], for modelling and validation. The type-4 vessel has 29 layers [7.5₇/15₆/25₄/35₁/45₁/90₁₀] with an experimental burst pressure of 81.9 MPa. Figure 2 shows the flowchart to predict the burst pressure of type-4 pressure and the approaches to improve the burst performance. The burst performance of the pressure vessel was predicted by an analytical model of the type-4 pressure vessel using Classical Laminate Theory (CLT) in MATLAB 2024. CLT is an analytical framework to predict the mechanical behaviour of the composite laminate under in-plane loading. CLT enables the determination of in-plane stresses, strains, and deformations in a laminate composed of multiple orthotropic laminae stacked at various orientations. The analytical model was developed based on the following assumptions: 1) each lamina behaves as a linear elastic orthotropic material, 2) Kirchhoff hypothesis, and 3) Perfect bonding [10].

Figure 2: Flowchart for burst pressure prediction and performance improvement strategies.

The fundamental equation of CLT is given by the equation (1). This equation is used to express in-plane strain and curvature at any location of the composite [11].

$$\begin{bmatrix} N_x \\ N_y \\ N_{xy} \\ M_x \\ M_y \\ M_{xy} \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} A_{11} & A_{12} & A_{16} & B_{11} & B_{12} & B_{16} \\ A_{12} & A_{22} & A_{26} & B_{12} & B_{22} & B_{26} \\ A_{16} & A_{26} & A_{66} & B_{16} & B_{26} & B_{66} \\ B_{11} & B_{12} & B_{16} & D_{11} & D_{12} & D_{16} \\ B_{12} & B_{22} & B_{26} & D_{12} & D_{22} & D_{26} \\ B_{16} & B_{26} & B_{66} & D_{16} & D_{26} & D_{66} \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} \varepsilon_x^0 \\ \varepsilon_y^0 \\ \gamma_{xy}^0 \\ k_x \\ k_y \\ k_{xy} \end{bmatrix} \quad (1)$$

$$A_{ij} = \sum_{k=1}^n [(\bar{Q}_{ij})]_k (h_k - h_{k-1}); \quad B_{ij} = \frac{1}{2} \sum_{k=1}^n [(\bar{Q}_{ij})]_k (h_k^2 - h_{k-1}^2);$$

$$D_{ij} = \frac{1}{3} \sum_{k=1}^n [(\bar{Q}_{ij})]_k (h_k^3 - h_{k-1}^3) \quad (2)$$

$$\begin{bmatrix} \varepsilon^0 \\ k \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} A_1 & B_1 \\ B_1 & D_1 \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} N \\ M \end{bmatrix} \quad (3)$$

Where [A], [B] and [D] are extensional, coupling and bending stiffness matrix, respectively. These stiffness matrices are a function of the transformed reduced stiffness matrix $[\bar{Q}]$ and the total number of layers n, where h represents the thickness of each layer. Finally, the stress-strain on each layer is calculated by using equation (4). Where z is total thickness of the composite.

$$\begin{bmatrix} \sigma_x \\ \sigma_y \\ \tau_{xy} \end{bmatrix} = [\bar{Q}] \begin{bmatrix} \varepsilon_{x0} \\ \varepsilon_{y0} \\ \gamma_{xy0} \end{bmatrix} + z[\bar{Q}] \begin{bmatrix} k_x \\ k_y \\ k_{xy} \end{bmatrix} \quad (4)$$

$$\begin{bmatrix} \varepsilon_x \\ \varepsilon_y \\ \gamma_{xy} \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} \varepsilon_{x0} \\ \varepsilon_{y0} \\ \gamma_{xy0} \end{bmatrix} + z \begin{bmatrix} k_x \\ k_y \\ k_{xy} \end{bmatrix} \quad (5)$$

Once the stress and strain in the composite are calculated, then failure theories can be implemented to find the burst pressure of the composite. However, conventional isotropic failure criteria are inadequate for the anisotropic and heterogeneous nature of fiber-reinforced composites. Therefore, Maximum stress, Tsai Wu, Tsai Hill, and Hashin failure criteria were used to predict the failure. Each criterion has a different approach in defining how and when failure occurs in a composite lamina [12], [13].

Maximum stress failure criteria: is a noninteractive, simplest and conservative failure theory that assumes failure when any individual stress component in the local lamina coordinate system exceed its corresponding ultimate strength limit as given by equation (6).

$$-(\sigma_1^c)_{ult} < \sigma_1 < (\sigma_1^T)_{ult}; \quad -(\sigma_2^c)_{ult} < \sigma_2 < (\sigma_2^T)_{ult}; \quad -(\tau_{12}^c)_{ult} < \tau_{12} < (\tau_{12}^T)_{ult} \quad (6)$$

Tsai Wu failure criteria: is an interactive theory which includes linear and quadratic terms to account for different strength in tension and compression. This theory assumes the failure of composite when the left side terms of equation (7) is less than 1. This criterion considers tension-compression asymmetry and stress interactions, making it more accurate but computationally intensive.

$$(F_2 + F_3)\sigma_1^2 + (F_1 + F_3)\sigma_2^2 + (F_1 + F_2)\sigma_3^2 - 2F_3\sigma_1\sigma_2 - 2F_2\sigma_1\sigma_3 - 2F_1\sigma_2\sigma_3 +$$

$$2F_4\tau_{23}^2 + 2F_5\tau_{13}^2 + 2F_6\tau_{12}^2 < 1 \quad (7)$$

$$F_1 = \frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{2}{[(\sigma_2^T)_{ult}]^2} - \frac{1}{[(\sigma_1^T)_{ult}]^2} \right); F_2 = \frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{2}{[(\sigma_2^T)_{ult}]^2} \right); F_3 = \frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{2}{[(\sigma_1^T)_{ult}]^2} \right); F_6 = \frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{2}{[(\tau_{12})_{ult}]^2} \right) \quad (8)$$

Tsai Hill failure criteria: is an interactive with stress component. The theory is based on von Mises distortion energy theory, which predicts the failure when left side term of equation (9) is less than 1.

$$H_1\sigma_1 + H_2\sigma_2 + H_6\tau_{12} + H_{11}\sigma_1^2 + H_{22}\sigma_2^2 + H_{66}\tau_{12}^2 + 2H_{12}\sigma_1\sigma_2 < 1 \quad (9)$$

$$H_1 = \frac{1}{(\sigma_1^T)_{ult}} - \frac{1}{(\sigma_1^C)_{ult}}; H_2 = \frac{1}{(\sigma_2^T)_{ult}} - \frac{1}{(\sigma_2^C)_{ult}}; H_{11} = \frac{1}{(\sigma_1^T)_{ult}(\sigma_1^C)_{ult}}; H_{22} = \frac{1}{(\sigma_2^T)_{ult}(\sigma_2^C)_{ult}}; H_{66} = \frac{1}{[(\tau_{12})_{ult}]^2}; H_6 = 0 \quad (10)$$

Hashin failure criteria: distinguish between different failure modes such as fiber tension, fiber compression, matrix tension and matrix compression given by equation (11). Mostly used for progressive damage model and finite element simulation.

$$\left(\frac{\sigma_1}{(\sigma_1^T)_{ult}} \right)^2 \geq 1; \left(\frac{\sigma_1}{(\sigma_1^C)_{ult}} \right)^2 \geq 1 \quad (11)$$

$$\left(\frac{\sigma_1}{(\sigma_1^T)_{ult}} \right)^2 + \left(\frac{\tau_{12}}{(\tau_{12}^T)_{ult}} \right)^2 \geq 1; \left(\frac{\sigma_2}{2(\sigma_2^C)_{ult}} \right)^2 + \left(\frac{\tau_{12}}{(\tau_{12}^T)_{ult}} \right)^2 \geq 1 \quad (12)$$

2.2.1. APPROACH-1: PROGRESSIVE PLY FAILURE

Composite is an anisotropic material in which the failure initiates from the weakest lamina and progresses through the entire laminate in a random manner. 1st ply failure in the progressive ply failure (PPF) mechanism identifies the onset of the damage in the laminate. This method provides a more realistic prediction of initial damage than global failure criteria, especially in pressure vessels where localized stress concentrations may cause early damage initiation. In this approach, PPF is calculated by using failure criteria and replacing that ply orientation with another angle to investigate the role of sequence. This method is a conventional and time-consuming method to find the best burst performance. However, this strategy is integrated with a genetic algorithm to automate the process to optimize the sequence based on targeted burst pressure. However, the PPF method helps to identify the weakest ply, its angle, and position [6], [11], [14].

2.2.2. APPROACH-2: GENETIC ALGORITHM

The stacking sequence of composite laminates plays a crucial role in determining the mechanical performance and burst pressure of Type-4 hydrogen pressure vessels. Due to the combinatorial nature of stacking possibilities, Genetic Algorithm (GA) was employed to efficiently explore the design space. In this approach, each chromosome (ply) encodes a candidate layer sequence, with fiber orientations represented as discrete values [7.5/15/25/35/45/90]₁₀. The algorithm iteratively evolves the population through selection, crossover, and mutation operations, guided by a fitness function based on performance metrics such as burst pressure and compliance with failure criteria. To assess its fitness value, an objective function is utilized. If the convergence criterion is not met, the algorithm applies genetic operators again to produce a new generation. This process repeats for multiple generations until either the convergence criterion is satisfied, or the maximum number of generations is reached. Figure 3 illustrates the flowchart of the proposed genetic algorithm (GA). This approach provides a robust and flexible framework for the design optimization of composite pressure vessels. At last, the top 10 data sets were selected for data processing, in which the pressure vessel dome geometry is designed in ANSYS to identify the uneven dome geometry at the corresponding layer sequence [15], [16], [17].

Figure 3: Flowchart for the genetic algorithm for composite sequence optimization.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

In this section, the analytical CLT model of a type-4 hydrogen pressure vessel is validated with the experimental burst pressure and finite element analysis provided by reference. The validated model is incorporated with the first ply failure strategy, followed by a genetic algorithm to improve the performance of the type-4 hydrogen pressure vessel by optimizing the layer sequence.

3.1. MODEL VALIDATION

Figure 4 (A) depicts the comparison of the analytical CLT model with the finite element and experimental burst pressure of a type-4 pressure vessel. The analysis shows that the model follows the Hashin matrix failure, which is also reported in the reference design. The burst pressure predicted by the analytical model is 75.61 MPa compared to finite element (75.3 MPa) and experimental (81.9 MPa) [9]. The model shows a good agreement with failure theory, with an error of less than 1 % with finite element and 8.3 % with experimental burst pressure. The model is also designed using finite element analysis in ANSYS to identify the safe and unsafe model of the failure. Figure 4 (B) and (C) shows that the failure of the type-4 pressure vessel lies in the cylindrical section, which corresponds to a safe failure model. Moreover, the investigation found that the Hashin failure is more realistic to predict the burst pressure due to its distinct nature in the failure model. However, the other failure theories are over-predicted, such as maximum stress due to no interaction with stress components.

Figure 4: (A) comparison for failure criteria for analytical CLT with reference, (B) failure mode using finite element and (C) experimental burst tested type-4 pressure vessel.

3.2. APPROACH-1: PROGRESSIVE PLY FAILURE

The Figure 5 represents the theoretical burst pressure for different stacking sequences, changed by replacing the orientation of the first ply failure. Their corresponding values are given in Table 2. In this approach, the ply that fails first was replaced by the ply that fails last or has a different orientation, because that ply has taken the most stress till the end of the complete composite failure. The analysis shows the burst performance has been improved by 16.28 % compared to the finite element in reference for stack-2. After stack -2, it is observed that the maximum stress failure is significantly reduced which is even below the nominal burst pressure (2 time of operating pressure) as per ISO 11119-3. Therefore, the stack-3 to 5 is considered for the applicable layer sequence.

Figure 5: Bust performance improvement by PPF mechanism.

Table 2: Comparison of burst performance for different stacking sequences based on PPF.

	Stacking sequence [90 ₁₀ /45 ₁ /35 ₁ /25 ₄ /15 ₆ /7.5 ₇]	Max. stress	Tsai Wu	Tsai Hill	Hashin (matrix failure)	Experimental burst test
	Reference	73.58	55.75	67.5	75.3	81.9
1	Stacking -1	85.60	52.43	61.61	75.61	
2	Stacking -2	83.27	52.81	62.82	87.56	
3	Stacking-3	51.1	78.25	96.20	103.58	
4	Stacking-4	50.64	79.97	96.34	108.57	
5	Stacking-5	49.85	101.01	97.98	113.76	

This strategy is complex, time-consuming, and fails to provide the optimum layer sequence for best performance. Therefore, the PPF is integrated with a genetic algorithm to optimize the sequence.

3.3. APPROACH-2: GENETIC ALGORITHM (GA)

In GA, the first 10 layers were fixed as they are important to generate the symmetry of the dome with the cylindrical shape, and the last layer was also fixed with 90⁰ orientation because that layer helps to hold the helical layer and avoid its slippage. Since, 18 layers left for implementing the GA, those layers were considered as genes of the system.

Figure 6: (A) initial population using brute force technique and (B) fitness profile for different failure criteria.

Firstly, an initial population was created using brute force technique in which random combinations are generated with all plies keeping the total number of layers the same as 29. Figure 6 (A) shows the initial population representing the theoretical burst pressure at different failure criteria. In the initial population, 100 data set points called chromosomes were filtered, which have the lowest possible burst pressure of 70 MPa under any failure criteria to meet the ISO 11119-3. These chromosomes are evaluated using a fitness function that quantifies their burst performance based on objectives function. Tournament selection technique was employed to choose the parent solution based on their fitness as shown in Figure 6 (B). Now, the genes of the parents were crossover to generate a new population with different genes. To maintain diversity and avoid premature convergence, random mutations were introduced with a constraint that the new population/sequence cannot create any sequence that has more than two orientations simultaneously. This constraint helps to avoid the nonuniformity in the cylindrical shape. The best performing chromosomes were retained using elitism, and the population is iteratively evolved over successive generations. This process continues until a burst pressure approaches constant value with a convergence of 10^{-3} as shown in Figure 6 (B). Where the average burst pressure approaches steady state after 100 generations. After the completion of the process, the optimum layer sequence is identified which have lowest possible burst pressure of 70 MPa So that the actual type-4 with optimum winding sequence should not have burst pressure less than safety factor. Table 3 listed burst pressure at the optimum layer sequence compared with progressive ply failure and reference data.

The analysis found the GA has improved the burst performance by 28.89 % compared to reference holding Hashin failure criteria.

Table 3: Comparison of burst performance.

Failure Theory	Burst pressure (MPa)				Burst performance Improvement (%)	
	Experimental	Reference	Analytical CLT model	Approach-1: PPF		Approach-2: GA
Max Stress 1		95.37	103.02	98.64	101.41	+ 6.33
Max Stress 2	81.9	73.58	85.6	83.27	83.25	+ 13.14
Tsai-Wu		55.75	52.43	52.81	82.89	+ 48.68
Tsai-Hill		67.5	61.61	62.82	87.24	+ 29.24
Hashin		75.3	75.61	87.56	97.05	+ 28.89

4. CONCLUSION

An analytical CLT model for a Type-IV hydrogen pressure vessel was validated against experimental and finite element results, showing excellent agreement within 1% of FEA and 8.3% of experimental data. The Hashin failure criterion accurately captured matrix-dominated failure in the cylindrical section, aligning with the observed failure modes. A progressive ply failure (PPF) approach provided up to 16.28% improvement in burst pressure but was limited in efficiency. To overcome this, a Genetic Algorithm (GA) was integrated, optimizing the stacking sequence while maintaining structural constraints. The GA-based method achieved a 28.89% improvement in burst pressure compared to the reference design using Hashin failure. This study demonstrates that combining analytical modeling, PPF theory, and evolutionary optimization effectively enhances the structural performance of Type-IV composite pressure vessels.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

This work is supported and funded by the Technology Mission Division (Energy, Water & all Others), Department of Science & Technology, Ministry of Science & Technology and Government of India under the project Integrated Clean-Energy Material Acceleration Platform (IC-MAP) on Bioenergy & H₂, Project reference number: DST/TMD/IC-MAP/2K20/02(C).

REFERENCES

- [1] D. Mori and K. Hirose, "Recent challenges of hydrogen storage technologies for fuel cell vehicles," *Int. J. Hydrogen Energy*, vol. 34, no. 10, pp. 4569–4574, 2009, doi: 10.1016/j.ijhydene.2008.07.115.
- [2] P. Sharma, A. K. Burolia, A. Mandal, and S. Neogi, "Commercially available resources for physical hydrogen storage and distribution," in *Towards Hydrogen Infrastructure: Advances and Challenges in Preparing for the Hydrogen Economy*, Elsevier, 2023, pp. 225–256. doi: 10.1016/B978-0-323-95553-9.00010-8.
- [3] J. Bellosta von Colbe *et al.*, "Application of hydrides in hydrogen storage and compression: Achievements, outlook and perspectives," *Int. J. Hydrogen Energy*, vol. 44, no. 15, pp. 7780–7808, 2019, doi: 10.1016/j.ijhydene.2019.01.104.
- [4] D. Leh, P. Saffré, P. Francescato, R. Arrieux, and S. Villalonga, "A progressive failure analysis of a 700-bar type IV hydrogen composite pressure vessel," *Int. J. Hydrogen Energy*, vol. 40, no. 38, pp. 13206–13214, 2015, doi: 10.1016/j.ijhydene.2015.05.061.
- [5] M. Nebe, T. J. Asijee, C. Braun, J. M. J. F. van Campen, and F. Walther, "Experimental and analytical analysis on the stacking sequence of composite pressure vessels," *Compos. Struct.*, vol. 247, p. 112429, 2020, doi: 10.1016/j.compstruct.2020.112429.
- [6] R. R. Chang, "Experimental and theoretical analyses of first-ply failure of laminated composite

- pressure vessels,” *Compos. Struct.*, vol. 49, no. 2, pp. 237–243, 2000, doi: 10.1016/S0263-8223(99)00133-6.
- [7] V. Alcántar, S. M. Aceves, E. Ledesma, S. Ledesma, and E. Aguilera, “Optimization of Type 4 composite pressure vessels using genetic algorithms and simulated annealing,” *Int. J. Hydrogen Energy*, vol. 42, no. 24, pp. 15770–15781, 2017, doi: 10.1016/j.ijhydene.2017.03.032.
- [8] F. D. Li *et al.*, “Optimal design of thin-layered composites for type IV vessels: Finite element analysis enhanced by ANN,” *Thin-Walled Struct.*, vol. 187, Jun. 2023, doi: 10.1016/j.tws.2023.110752.
- [9] P. Sharma, A. K. Burolia, N. C. Adak, J. Daiya, H. H. Sardar, and S. Neogi, “Effect of tension on liner buckling and performance of a type-4 cylinder for storage of compressed gases with experimental validation,” *Thin-Walled Struct.*, vol. 189, Aug. 2023, doi: 10.1016/j.tws.2023.110928.
- [10] S. Adali, E. B. Summers, and V. E. Verijenko, “Optimisation of laminated cylindrical pressure vessels under strength criterion,” *Compos. Struct.*, vol. 25, no. 1–4, pp. 305–312, 1993, doi: 10.1016/0263-8223(93)90177-R.
- [11] T. Y. Kam, Y. W. Liu, and F. T. Lee, “First-ply failure strength of laminated composite pressure vessels,” *Compos. Struct.*, vol. 38, no. 1–4, pp. 65–70, 1997, doi: 10.1016/S0263-8223(97)00042-1.
- [12] L. Wang, C. Zheng, S. Wei, and Z. Wei, “Micromechanics-based progressive failure analysis of carbon fiber/epoxy composite vessel under combined internal pressure and thermomechanical loading,” *Compos. Part B Eng.*, vol. 89, pp. 77–84, 2016, doi: 10.1016/j.compositesb.2015.11.018.
- [13] Z. Hu *et al.*, “Investigation on failure behaviors of 70 MPa Type IV carbon fiber overwound hydrogen storage vessels,” *Compos. Struct.*, vol. 259, no. November 2020, pp. 1–11, 2021, doi: 10.1016/j.compstruct.2020.113387.
- [14] S. Lin, L. Yang, H. Xu, X. Jia, X. Yang, and L. Zu, “Progressive damage analysis for multiscale modelling of composite pressure vessels based on Puck failure criterion,” *Compos. Struct.*, vol. 255, no. September 2020, p. 113046, 2021, doi: 10.1016/j.compstruct.2020.113046.
- [15] M. H. Hajmohammad, A. Tabatabaeian, A. R. Ghasemi, and F. Taheri-Behrooz, “A novel detailed analytical approach for determining the optimal design of FRP pressure vessels subjected to hydrostatic loading: Analytical model with experimental validation,” *Compos. Part B Eng.*, vol. 183, no. December 2019, 2020, doi: 10.1016/j.compositesb.2019.107732.
- [16] P. F. Liu, J. K. Chu, S. J. Hou, P. Xu, and J. Y. Zheng, “Numerical simulation and optimal design for composite high-pressure hydrogen storage vessel: A review,” *Renew. Sustain. Energy Rev.*, vol. 16, no. 4, pp. 1817–1827, 2012, doi: 10.1016/j.rser.2012.01.006.
- [17] C. U. Kim, C. S. Hong, C. G. Kim, and J. Y. Kim, “Optimal design of filament wound type 3 tanks under internal pressure using a modified genetic algorithm,” *Compos. Struct.*, vol. 71, no. 1, pp. 16–25, 2005, doi: 10.1016/j.compstruct.2004.09.006.
- [1] D. Mori and K. Hirose, “Recent challenges of hydrogen storage technologies for fuel cell vehicles,” *Int. J. Hydrogen Energy*, vol. 34, no. 10, pp. 4569–4574, 2009, doi: 10.1016/j.ijhydene.2008.07.115.
- [2] P. Sharma, A. K. Burolia, A. Mandal, and S. Neogi, “Commercially available resources for physical hydrogen storage and distribution,” in *Towards Hydrogen Infrastructure: Advances and Challenges in Preparing for the Hydrogen Economy*, Elsevier, 2023, pp. 225–256. doi: 10.1016/B978-0-323-95553-9.00010-8.
- [3] J. Bellosta von Colbe *et al.*, “Application of hydrides in hydrogen storage and compression: Achievements, outlook and perspectives,” *Int. J. Hydrogen Energy*, vol. 44, no. 15, pp. 7780–7808, 2019, doi: 10.1016/j.ijhydene.2019.01.104.
- [4] D. Leh, P. Saffré, P. Francescato, R. Arrieux, and S. Villalonga, “A progressive failure analysis of a 700-bar type IV hydrogen composite pressure vessel,” *Int. J. Hydrogen Energy*, vol. 40, no. 38, pp. 13206–13214, 2015, doi: 10.1016/j.ijhydene.2015.05.061.
- [5] M. Nebe, T. J. Asijee, C. Braun, J. M. J. F. van Campen, and F. Walther, “Experimental and analytical analysis on the stacking sequence of composite pressure vessels,” *Compos. Struct.*, vol. 247, p. 112429, 2020, doi: 10.1016/j.compstruct.2020.112429.

- [6] R. R. Chang, "Experimental and theoretical analyses of first-ply failure of laminated composite pressure vessels," *Compos. Struct.*, vol. 49, no. 2, pp. 237–243, 2000, doi: 10.1016/S0263-8223(99)00133-6.
- [7] V. Alcántar, S. M. Aceves, E. Ledesma, S. Ledesma, and E. Aguilera, "Optimization of Type 4 composite pressure vessels using genetic algorithms and simulated annealing," *Int. J. Hydrogen Energy*, vol. 42, no. 24, pp. 15770–15781, 2017, doi: 10.1016/j.ijhydene.2017.03.032.
- [8] F. D. Li *et al.*, "Optimal design of thin-layered composites for type IV vessels: Finite element analysis enhanced by ANN," *Thin-Walled Struct.*, vol. 187, Jun. 2023, doi: 10.1016/j.tws.2023.110752.
- [9] P. Sharma, A. K. Burolia, N. C. Adak, J. Daiya, H. H. Sardar, and S. Neogi, "Effect of tension on liner buckling and performance of a type-4 cylinder for storage of compressed gases with experimental validation," *Thin-Walled Struct.*, vol. 189, Aug. 2023, doi: 10.1016/j.tws.2023.110928.
- [10] S. Adali, E. B. Summers, and V. E. Verijenko, "Optimisation of laminated cylindrical pressure vessels under strength criterion," *Compos. Struct.*, vol. 25, no. 1–4, pp. 305–312, 1993, doi: 10.1016/0263-8223(93)90177-R.
- [11] T. Y. Kam, Y. W. Liu, and F. T. Lee, "First-ply failure strength of laminated composite pressure vessels," *Compos. Struct.*, vol. 38, no. 1–4, pp. 65–70, 1997, doi: 10.1016/S0263-8223(97)00042-1.
- [12] L. Wang, C. Zheng, S. Wei, and Z. Wei, "Micromechanics-based progressive failure analysis of carbon fiber/epoxy composite vessel under combined internal pressure and thermomechanical loading," *Compos. Part B Eng.*, vol. 89, pp. 77–84, 2016, doi: 10.1016/j.compositesb.2015.11.018.
- [13] Z. Hu *et al.*, "Investigation on failure behaviors of 70 MPa Type IV carbon fiber overwound hydrogen storage vessels," *Compos. Struct.*, vol. 259, no. November 2020, pp. 1–11, 2021, doi: 10.1016/j.compstruct.2020.113387.
- [14] S. Lin, L. Yang, H. Xu, X. Jia, X. Yang, and L. Zu, "Progressive damage analysis for multiscale modelling of composite pressure vessels based on Puck failure criterion," *Compos. Struct.*, vol. 255, no. September 2020, p. 113046, 2021, doi: 10.1016/j.compstruct.2020.113046.
- [15] M. H. Hajmohammad, A. Tabatabaeian, A. R. Ghasemi, and F. Taheri-Behrooz, "A novel detailed analytical approach for determining the optimal design of FRP pressure vessels subjected to hydrostatic loading: Analytical model with experimental validation," *Compos. Part B Eng.*, vol. 183, no. December 2019, 2020, doi: 10.1016/j.compositesb.2019.107732.
- [16] P. F. Liu, J. K. Chu, S. J. Hou, P. Xu, and J. Y. Zheng, "Numerical simulation and optimal design for composite high-pressure hydrogen storage vessel: A review," *Renew. Sustain. Energy Rev.*, vol. 16, no. 4, pp. 1817–1827, 2012, doi: 10.1016/j.rser.2012.01.006.
- [17] C. U. Kim, C. S. Hong, C. G. Kim, and J. Y. Kim, "Optimal design of filament wound type 3 tanks under internal pressure using a modified genetic algorithm," *Compos. Struct.*, vol. 71, no. 1, pp. 16–25, 2005, doi: 10.1016/j.compstruct.2004.09.006.